

**YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM – TARBIYA
MUASSASALARIGA QARATILAYATGAN E'TIBOR**

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Annotatsiya. Bugungi bog'cha yoshidagi bolalarning ziyrakligi, axborot texnologiyalarini o'zlashtirib olayotgani maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida o'quv-tarbiya dasturlarini ilg'or xorijiy tajribalar asosida takomillashtirishni talab etmoqda.

Mamlakatimiz rahbari qaroriga ko'ra 2017-2021 yillarga mo'jallangan keng ko'lamli kompleks tadbirlardan iborat dastur zamirida ham bolalarni maktabga tayyorlash sifatini tubdan yaxshilash, ta'lim tarbiya jarayoniga zamonaviy yondashuvlarni tadbir etish, bolalarni intellektual, axloqiy, estetik va jismoniy rivojlantirish uchun barcha shart-sharoitni yaratish maqsadi mujassamdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Muassasa, Harakatlar strategiyasi Yangi O'zbekiston, kapital rekonstruksiya.

**ATTENTION PAID TO PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN NEW
UZBEKISTAN**

Abstract. Today's kindergarten age children's ingenuity and mastering of information technologies require the improvement of educational programs in preschool educational institutions based on advanced foreign experiences.

According to the decision of the head of our country, children will be sent to school as part of the program consisting of large-scale complex activities planned for 2017-2021. the goal of radically improving the quality of training, applying modern approaches to the educational process, creating all the conditions for the intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children is embodied.

Key words: Institution, Action strategy, New Uzbekistan, capital reconstruction.

**ВНИМАНИЕ ДОШКОЛЬНЫМ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫМ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯМ НОВОГО
УЗБЕКИСТАНА**

Аннотация. Сегодняшняя изобретательность детей детсадовского возраста и овладение информационными технологиями требуют совершенствования образовательных программ в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях на основе передового зарубежного опыта.

По решению главы нашей страны дети будут отправлены в школу в рамках программы, состоящей из масштабных комплексных мероприятий, запланированных на 2017-2021 годы. воплощена цель радикального повышения качества обучения, применения современных подходов к образовательному процессу, создания всех условий для интеллектуального, нравственного, эстетического и физического развития детей.

Ключевые слова: Учреждение, Стратегия действий, Новый Узбекистан, капитальная реконструкция.

O`quv – tarbiya muassasasining moddiy-texnika bazasi - ta`lim mazmuniga ta`sir etuvchi asosiy omillardan biridir. Shu sababli respublika miqiyosida maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalari moddiy - texnika bazasini mustahkamlashga alohida e`tibor qaratildi va bu borada qator qonun va farmonlar qabul qilindi. Ularning ijrosi har vaqt Vazirlikning kengaytirilgan yig`ilishlarida muhokama qilib borilgan bo`lsada,¹ soha ancha ortda qolgani ma`lum bo`ldi.

Shu sababli sohada yo`l qo`yilgan kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish zaruriyatga aylandi.

Binobarin, Prezidentimiz Sh.M.Mirziyoyevning “2017-2021 yillarda maktabgacha ta`lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to`g`risida” gi² qarorining qabul qilingani xalqimizni mamnun etdi.

Maktabgacha tarbiya ta`lim tizimining birlamchi va eng muhim bo`g`ini hisoblanadi. Sog`lom genfondni, yetuk kadrlarni tarbiyalash, avvalo, shu tizimdan boshlanadi. Biroq Prezidentimiz Sh.M. Mirziyoyev ta`kidlaganlaridek, oxirgi 20 yil davomida davlat tasarrufidagi maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalari soni 45 foizga kamaygan. Oqibatda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning 33 foizi bog`chalarga qamrab olingan, xolos. Bu ko`rsatgich Daniyada 99 foiz, Yaponiyada 97 foiz, Janubiy Koreyada 95 foizni tashkil etadi. Xususan, joylardagi maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalarida kadrlar ta`minoti va salohiyati yetarli emasligi, sohada 57 mingdan ortiq mutaxassislar mehnat qilayotgan bo`lsa-da, ularning 85 foizini o`rta ma`lumotli kadrlar tashkil etayotgani farzandlarimizni maktab ta`limiga talab darajasida tayyorlash imkonini bermayotir” deb ta`kidlandi.³

Bugungi bog`cha yoshidagi bolalarning ziyrakligi, axborot texnologiyalarini o`zlashtirib olayotgani maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalarida o`quv-tarbiya dasturlarini ilg`or xorijiy tajribalar asosida takomillashtirishni talab etmoqda.

Mamlakatimiz rahbari qaroriga ko`ra 2017-2021 yillarga mo`jallangan keng ko`lamli kompleks tadbirlardan iborat dastur zahirida ham bolalarni maktabga tayyorlash sifatini tubdan yaxshilash, ta`lim tarbiya jarayoniga zamonaviy yondashuvlarni tadbiriq etish, bolalarni intellektual, axloqiy, estetik va jismoniy rivojlantirish uchun barcha shart-sharoitni yaratish maqsadi mujassamdir. Dasturga binoan, 2 ming 200 ta maktabgacha ta`lim muassasasining moddiy - texnika bazasini mustahkamlash, qishloq joylarda maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalarini yangidan qurish, zarur inventar, jihozlar, o`quv metodik, qo`llanma va multimediyali vositalar bilan ta`minlash rejalashtirilgan. 2018 yil Dalat byudjetidan 427 bog`chada qurilish-ta`mirlash ishlarini bajarish uchun 771 milliard so`m mablag` ajratish (jumladan, 14 tasini yangidan qurish, 256 tasini rekonstruksiya qilish va 157 tasini kapital ta`mirlash) bo`yicha topshiriq berildi¹.

Mustaqillik yillarida yurtimizda ta`lim-tarbiya tizimini tubdan takomil-lashtirish, ertangi kunimizning munosib davomchilarini kamolga yetkazishning mustahkam tashkiliy-huquqiy mexanizmi yaratildi. Sohaga oid qabul qilingan qator davlat dasturlariga binoan salmoqli ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Sababi dunyo taraqqiyoti shiddati barcha soha kabi ta`lim-tarbiya

¹ Эргашев Ф. Обидов Д. Миллий таълим тарихидан. Т., «Академия», 1998.19 - бет

² O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoevning “2017-2021 yillarda maktabgacha ta`lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to`g`risida” gi Farmoni.//Xalq so`zi. 2017yil,30 sentyabr.

³ Xalq so`zi. 2017 yil, 20 dekabr № 255// Mamlakat kelajagiga mustahkam zamin.

¹ O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoevning “2017-2021 yillarda maktabgacha ta`lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to`g`risida” gi Farmoni.//Xalq so`zi. 2017yil,30 sentyabr.

jarayoniga ham yangicha yondashuvni, innovatsion texnologiyalarni tadbiq qilishni taqozo etayapti. Binobarin, birinchi navbatda yosh avlodni komil inson qilib tarbiyalash, ularni kasb jihatdan tayyorgarlikka bog'liq bo'ladi. Bu esa butun ta'lim tizimini tubdan isloh qilishni taqozo etmoqda.

Ushbu sa'y-harakatlarning amalga oshirilishi natijasida bolalarni maktabgacha ta'limga qamrab olish 1,5 barobar ortadi. 2021 yilga borib, respublikamizda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari 1 million 109 ming nafardan ortiq bolalarni qamrab olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Ayni paytda viloyatlar va shahar kengashlari hokimliklari zimmasiga bolalarni maktabgacha ta'limga qamrab olish darajasini keskin oshirish bo'yicha hududiy dasturlar ishlab chiqildi. Bunda har bir tuman va shaharda 10-15 ta yangi, jumladan, davlat-xususiy sherikchilik mexanizmi asosida maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasini tashkil etish vazifasi belgilab olindi.

Albatta o'tgan yillar davomida O'zbekiston Respublikasida ta'limga sarflanayotgan xarajatlar miqdori 2001 yilda – 330453,2 mln. so'm, 2002 yilda 491960,8 so'mni va 2003 yilda 645900,0 mln. so'mni tashkil etgan. Kapital remont xarajatlarning umumiy xarajatlar tarkibidagi ulushi 1997 yil - 490,90 mln. so'mni, 1998 yil – 1204,30 mln. so'mni, 1999 yil – 1437.10 mln. so'mni, 2000 yil – 1417,50 mln. so'mni, 2001 – yil 2931,40 mln. so'mni, 2002 yil - 1586, 10 mln. so'mni tashkil etdi¹.

2017 yilgi maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarini mukammal ta'mirlash dasturiga asosan viloyatdagi 10 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlari olib borilgan.

Mazkur qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlariga viloyat mahalliy byudjeti mablag'lari hisobidan 7292,0 mln. so'm mablag' yo'naltirildi va ob'yektlar to'liq mukammal ta'mirlanib jihozlab berildi. Bundan tashqari, 2016 yilgi maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarini mukammal ta'mirlash dasturiga asosan viloyatdagi 10 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlari olib borilgan.

Jumladan:

- 1) Navoiy shahar 5-sonli MTM
- 2) Nurota tumani 1-sonli MTM
- 3) Nurota tumani 2-sonli MTM
- 4) Navoiy shahar 16-sonli MMTM
- 5) Zarafshon shahri 1-sonli MTM
- 6) Konimex tumani 9-sonli MTM
- 7) Qiziltepa tumani 4-sonli MTM
- 8) Karmana tumani 5-sonli MTM
- 9) Xatirchi tumani 5-sonli MTM
- 10) Navbahor tumani 7-sonli MTM filiali

Ushbu qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlari uchun viloyat mahalliy byudjeti mablag'-lari hisobidan jami bo'lib 6,0 mlrd. so'm mablag' ajratildi. Bugungi kunda mazkur maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida qurilish - ta'mirlash ishlari yakunlanib jihozlash ishlari olib borilmoqda.

¹ Тўйчиев М.Б.«Ўзбекистон Республикасида ўрта махсус маорифини ривожлантириш учун ажратилган бюджет маблағларидан фойдаланишнинг самарадорлигини ошириш йўллари.Т. Автореферат. 2004. 9-бет.

Navoiy viloyatida ham dastur bo'yicha yuksak maqsadli vazifalar belgilab olingan.

Bugungi kunda viloyatimizdagi 130 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasiga 24 ming 442 nafar bola qamrab olingan. Bog'cha yoshidagi bolalar soni esa 65 ming 896 nafarni tashkil etadi. Bugunda qamrovni kengaytirish maqsadida qisqa muddatli guruhlar tashkil etilib, ularga 1049 nafar tarbiyalanuvchi qabul qilindi.¹

2018 yilda yana qo'shimcha ravishda 25 ta va undan ortiq qisqa muddatli guruhlar faoliyati yo'lga qo'yiladi. Natijada yana 1000-1250 nafar bolalarni maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga qamrab olish kutilmoqda.

Viloyatda 3-7 yoshdagi bolalar soni 70101 nafar ekanligini inobatga oladigan bo'lsak qamrov 37,1 % foizni tashkil etmoqda. Bolalarni ta'lim muassasalariga qamrovini tahlil qilganimizda Xatirchi tumanida 9.5foizni, Qiziltepa tumanida 16.4 foizni, Navbahor tumanida 18.2 foizni, Nurota tumanida 22.7 foizni, Konimex tumanida 28.2 foizni, Karmana tumanida 29.2 foizni tashkil etmoqda. Bu yangi qurilish, mavjud muassasalarni mukammal ta'mirlash, rekonstruksiya qilish hisobidan qo'shimcha quvvatlarni tashkil etish zaruratini keltirib chiqaradi albatta.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2016 yil, 29 dekabrda "2017-2021 yillarda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-2707-sonli qaroriga asosan, Navoiy viloyatida 2017-2021 yillarda viloyat bo'yicha jami 54 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida qurilish-ta'mirlash va jihozlash ishlari olib borilib 6 860 o'rinli quvvat tashkil etilishi va mazkur qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlariga 52 mlrd. 300,0 mln. so'm ajratilishi belgilab qo'yilgan bo'lib, shundan 1 ta yangi qurilish, 31 ta rekonstruksiya va 22 ta mukammal ta'mirlash ishlari amalga oshirilishi rejalashtirilgan.

2017 yil rejasidagi 10 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida amalga oshirilgan qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlariga 11,9 mlrd. so'm miqdorda mablag'lar yo'naltirilib, barcha ob'ektlar to'liq foydalanishga topshirildi. Bundan tashqari, 2018 yilgi Investitsiya dasturi loyihasiga viloyat bo'yicha jami 16 ta (12 ta rekonstruksiya va 4 ta mukammal ta'mirlash) maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida qurilish - ta'mirlash ishlari amalga oshiriladi. Bugungi kunda mazkur ob'ektlar bo'yicha loyiha-smeta hujjatlari ishlab chiqilgan. Buning natijasida bolalarni maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga qamrab olish ko'rsatkichi bosqichma-bosqich (65-70) foizga yetkaziladi. Albatta, bu ishlarimiz yana davom etadi.

Bundan tashqari, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2016 yil 23 dekabrda PQ-2697-sonli qaroriga muvofiq, 2017 yil Investitsiya dasturiga binoan viloyatdagi 10 ta (*shundan, 4 kapital rekonstruksiya va 6 ta mukammal ta'mirlash*) maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlari olib borilishi belgilangan. Ushbu qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlariga jami bo'lib, 9,1 mlrd. so'm mablag' ajratilishi rejalashtirilgan. Mazkur ishlar to'liq amalga oshirildi. Xuddi shundan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2016 yil 29 dekabrda PQ-2707-sonli qaroriga muvofiq **2017-2021** yillarda yangidan quriladigan, kapital rekonstruksiya qilinadigan va mukammal ta'mirlanadigan maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining ro'yxati belgilab qo'yilgan. Unga ko'ra, Navoiy viloyatida 2017-2021 yillarda 6 860 o'ringa mo'ljallangan jami bo'lib, 1 ta MTM (*120 o'rinli*) yangidan quriladi, 31 ta MTM (*jami 3 360 o'rinli*) rekonstruksiya qilinadi va

¹ Do'stlik bayrog'i. 2018 yil, 1 yanvar. № 1.// Maktabgacha ta'lim-porloq kelajak garovi.

22 ta MTM (3 380 o'rinli) mukammal ta'mirlanadi. 2017 yil Investitsiya dasturi hamda "Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish" dasturiga muvofiq viloyatimizdagi 10 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida (4 ta rekonstruksiya va 6 ta mukammal ta'mirlash) qurilish-ta'mirlash ishlari olib borilayotgan bo'lib, ushbu qurilishlarga 11 mlrd 723 mln. so'm mablag' yo'naltirilgan.

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